

XROTOR

X-shaped Radical Offshore Wind Turbine for Overall Cost of Energy Reduction

D2.8

Comparison of CFD computations and experimental results

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Month 36

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101007135

Document Information

Deliverable ID	2.8
Deliverable Title	Comparison of CFD computations and experimental results
Lead beneficiary	CENER
Contributing beneficiaries	TuDelft
Due date Annex I	2023.12.31
Issue date	2023.12.20
Dissemination level	Public /Confidential
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Approval

Version	Date	Description	Reviewed by	Approved by
1	2023.12.20		Prof. Bill Leithead and Dr James Carroll 	

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The X-Rotor Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101007135. For more information on the project, its partners, and contributors please see <https://xrotor-project.eu>.

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Table of Contents

1	DELIVERABLE DETAILS	8
2	NUMERICAL SIMULATION DESCRIPTION	8
2.1	SCALED PRIMARY ROTOR GEOMETRY DESCRIPTION	8
2.2	PRIMARY ROTOR SIMULATIONS DESCRIPTION	9
3	EXPERIMENTS DESCRIPTION AND RESULTS	11
3.1	Wind Tunnel.....	11
3.2	Scaled X-Rotor model.	12
3.3	Flow measurement system	12
3.4	Cases overview.....	13
3.5	Turbine load filtering.....	14
4	NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL SIMULATIONS COMPARISON	14
4.1	Campaign 2	15
4.2	Campaign 3	28
4.3	Forces comparison.	29
5	CONCLUSIONS	29
	Bibliography.....	30

About X-ROTOR

X-ROTOR: “X-shaped Radical Offshore wind Turbine for Overall cost of energy Reduction” is a Horizon 2020 funded project which aims to develop a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept.

The X-ROTOR project is led by University of Strathclyde (UK) in partnership with Norwegian University of Science and Technology (Norway), Delft University of Technology (Netherlands), University College Cork (Ireland), Fundacion Cener National Renewable Energy Centre (Spain) and GE Renovables España (Spain).

As the effects of climate change are becoming ever more visible, Europe has raised its target for the amount of energy it consumes from renewable sources from the previous goal of 27% to 32% by 2030. Offshore wind energy can play a key role in achieving the EU target and contribute to the required 40% reduction in CO₂ emissions. However, to achieve the previously mentioned targets the cost of offshore wind must be reduced. The X-ROTOR concept provides a direct route to drastically reducing both capital and operating costs of energy from offshore wind.

The project runs for three years from January 2021, during which time, the concept will be developed through a holistic consideration of technical, cost, environmental and socio-economic impact aspects.

If proven feasible, X-ROTOR will, as a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept, create new opportunities for the European wind energy industry and play an important role maintaining the EU’s position as global technological leader in renewable energy, reducing greenhouse gas emissions and decarbonising the EU economy.

For more information see <https://xrotor-project.eu>

Description of the deliverable and its purpose

This deliverable report supports deliverable D2.8 “**Comparison of CFD computations and experimental results**”. In this deliverable CFD high fidelity computations of the XROTOR concept will be used to support and validate the wind tunnel experiments. The results in the deliverable are a comparison of computations with the wind tunnel tests performed in WP2. The accuracy of the comparison will reveal robust computations and experiments.

This deliverable contains the XROTOR concept geometry descriptions, the mesh generation, the set up for the computations as well as the flow field conditions. In addition, the experimental campaign performed in TUDelft under the scope of the XROTOR project will be described. Finally, the comparisons between the experiments and simulations will be shown and discussed.

List of acronyms

DoA	Description of Action
O&M	Operation and Maintenance
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
OREC	Ocean Renewable Energy Coalition
WESC	Wind Energy Science Conference
WP	Work Package
XRC	X-ROTOR concept
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
PIV	Particle image velocimetry

1 DELIVERABLE DETAILS

The document is organized as follows: section 2 gives detailed analysis of the flow simulations in the XROTOR primary rotor (in the experiments used for comparison the secondary rotors are not included). Then, section 3 describes the experimental campaign performed in TUDelft and, finally, section 4 summarizes the comparison and the key outcomes and relevance of the XROTOR performance and main flow characteristics.

2 NUMERICAL SIMULATION DESCRIPTION

The following subsections describe the geometry, the meshes and the set-up used for the evaluation of the aerodynamic performance of the XROTOR primary rotor using CFD.

2.1 SCALED PRIMARY ROTOR GEOMETRY DESCRIPTION

The wind tunnel experiments modelled a simplified 1:100 scaled geometry of XRotor primary rotor. The blades were simplified by constant section blades with 0.075 m. chord NACA0021 airfoil. The top and bottom blades have a tip radius of $R = 0.75\text{m}$ and coning angles of 60° and 40° , respectively. The tower has a diameter of 0.06 m. The support system is a rectangular shaped structure with a length of 0.5 m, and has a central structural accretion in the attachment with the tower (as it can be seen in Figure 1)

The geometry of the scaled primary rotor geometry is summarized in Table 1.

Table 1 Geometry definition of the scaled primary rotor used for the wind tunnel experiments.0.1

Upper blade length	1 m
Lower blade length	0.653 m
Blade chord	0.075 m
Blade airfoil section	NACA0021
Tower diameter	0.06 m

Figure 1 Wind tunnel scaled primary rotor geometry.

2.2 PRIMARY ROTOR SIMULATIONS DESCRIPTION

2.2.1 Mesh definition

The mesh for the primary rotor is created using snappyHexMesh which is the mesher available to perform OpenFOAM simulations. It is a very fine mesh designed to obtain a detailed description of the flow and the blade forces in the primary rotor. Figure 2, Figure 3 and Figure 4 show different views of the mesh used for the primary rotor simulation and Table 2 summarizes the mesh main characteristics.

Figure 2 Primary rotor overall mesh view

Figure 3 Primary rotor mesh regions

Figure 4 Mesh in the upper blade airfoil

Table 2 Primary rotor mesh characteristics

Number of cells	22.68 Million cells
Blade covered by boundary layer	Upper-blade 94.8% Lower-blade 93.3%
Minimum distance to the wall	1.2e-4
Number of layers in the blade surface	5

2.2.2 Case set up.

The case studied to simulate the rotor aerodynamics characteristics and performance is described in Table 3.

Table 3 Full concept case definition

Wind velocity	4 [m/s]
Rotational Speed	21.333
Primary rotor	[rad/s]
Blade Pitch Angle	0°
Turbulence intensity	0.3%

The simulation performed for the primary rotor case is a transient simulation to capture the flow phenomena that appear since all blades work in the other blades wake. All the simulations are turbulent with the k-omega-SST model used. The dynamic mesh simulation is implemented using the available Arbitrary Mesh Interface technology from OpenFOAM. For the primary rotor the AMI defined is a vertical cylinder that includes the rotor. The boundary conditions settled in the domain boundaries are defined in Table 4.

Table 4 Boundary conditions used in the primary rotor simulation.

	Velocity	Pressure	Turbulence Model
Inlet	Free stream	Free stream	Fixed Value
Outlet	Free stream	Free stream	Inlet Outlet
Farfield/Sides	Free stream	Free stream	Inlet Outlet
Rotor	Moving Wall Velocity	Zero Gradient	kqRWallFunction omegaWallFunction
AMIs (arbitrary mesh interface)	Cyclic AMI	Cyclic AMI	Cyclic AMI

3 EXPERIMENTS DESCRIPTION AND RESULTS

3.1 Wind Tunnel

Experiments are performed in the Open Jet Facility (OJF) at TU Delft Aerospace Engineering Laboratories, illustrated in Figure 5. The atmospheric closed-loop wind tunnel has an octagonal exit section of 2.85m x 2.85m with a contraction ratio of 3:1. A controlled streamwise velocity of $U_{\infty} = 4\text{m/s}$ is used throughout the experiment. The resulting jet stream is bounded by shear layers with a semi-angle of 4.7° with turbulence intensities reported to be 0.5% within the testing region [3].

Figure 5 TUDelft wind tunnel view.

3.2 Scaled X-Rotor model.

A 1:100 scale X-Rotor model is mounted in the center of the test section, as illustrated in Figure 6. The model consists of four straight NACA0021 airfoil blades, with a constant chord of $c = 0.075\text{m}$ attached to a stiff crossbeam with the same profile and chord. The top and bottom blades have a tip radius of $R = 0.75\text{m}$ and coning angles of 60° and 40° , respectively. The rotor is supported via a tower with a diameter of 60mm . The model is mounted on a frame and driven at a constant tip-speed ratio of 4.0 , resulting in a chord-based Reynolds number of $Re = 8.1 \times 10^4$ at the tip. Instrumentation for measuring the shaft torque, rotational frequency, and turbine thrust vectoring is included in the frame. A detailed overview of the instrumentation is provided by LeBlanc et al [4].

3.3 Flow measurement system

A stereoscopic particle image velocimetry (PIV) system is used to measure several velocity fields at discrete cross-stream locations within the measurement volume of the VAWT model. Seeding is generated via a SAFEX smoke generator with an average particle diameter of $1\ \mu\text{m}$ and particle density $10^3\ \text{kgm}^{-3}$. The particles are illuminated with a Quantel Evergreen double-pulsed Nd:YAG laser with a sheet thickness of approximately $4\ \text{mm}$. Dual pulses with a wavelength of 523nm and 200mJ of energy are generated. Finally, images are captured at a frequency of $15\ \text{Hz}$ using two LaVision sCMOS cameras shooting from opposing sides of the laser sheet. With a focal length of $105\ \text{mm}$ and aperture 8 , the resulting field of view (FOV) is approximately $43\ \text{cm} \times 30\ \text{cm}$, yielding a digital image resolution of $6\ \text{px/mm}$. A time of $280\ \mu\text{s}$ between images is used.

The resulting images are processed with a cross-correlation-based image interrogation algorithm with window deformation, with sizes of $128\ \text{px}$ per $128\ \text{px}$ and $64\ \text{px}$ per $64\ \text{px}$ and an overlap factor of $75\ \%$. A total of 120 vector field images were captured for each measurement plane and averaged. The camera and laser systems are rigidly connected and mounted on a traversing system enabling a translation range in the x-axis and y-axis of $1.5\ \text{m}$

and 0.5 m, respectively. Translation in the z-axis is achieved manually by shifting the rigid connection between the systems.

3.4 Cases overview

The measurement system is used to capture phase-locked ($\theta = \text{constant}$) measurements of the flow field at varying locations of the X-Rotor (planes perpendicular to incident wind direction, i.e. $x = \text{constant}$). At a given cross-stream location, several planes are measured in the y-axis and z-axis directions via the traversing system and stitched together. Note due to time and memory constraints, not all phase and wake locations were measured in the same detail, with varying numbers of planes measured for each wake and phase pair. Further, due to the orientation of the cameras concerning the measurement planes, frequent masking operations are applied to the measurements to avoid shadows. Due to the placement of the PIV system, measurements focus on the windward half of the cycle, reaching up to approx. $y/R = -0.53$.

Figure 6 Wind tunnel top view. Left: campaign 2 measurements. Right: campaign 3 measurements

Data from two different testing campaigns are presented here ('Campaign 2' and 'Campaign 3'). Table 5 shows cross-stream locations and phases measured at each test campaign. From 'campaign 2' there are measurements at cross-stream locations within the rotor at four rotor positions (phases). Measurements from 'campaign 3' are taken at locations downstream the rotor and only at phase = 0° rotor position. Figure 6 shows with green lines the cross-stream locations for both campaigns. Figure 7 shows some of the cross-stream planes measured on 'campaign 3'.

Table 5 Measured locations at each experimental test campaign.

	Cross-stream locations (x position)	Phases (θ)
Campaign 2	x [mm] = -650 / -400 / -100 / 0 / 100 / 400 / 650	0°, 45°, 90°, 135°
	x/R [] = -0.867 / -0.533 / -0.133 / 0 / 0.133 / 0.533 / 0.867	
Campaign 3	x [mm] = 387 / 600 / 750 / 900 / 1050 / 1350 / 1500 / 1800 / 2100 / 2400	0°
	x/R [] = 0.516 / 0.8 / 1 / 1.2 / 1.4 / 1.8 / 2 / 2.4 / 2.8 / 3.2	

Figure 7 Visualization sections in the XROTOR wake.

3.5 Turbine load filtering

Before drawing conclusions about the induction field of the X-Rotor, the thrust vectoring of the scaled model must be discussed. The resolved thrust vectoring and thrust magnitude of the X-Rotor at a constant tip-speed ratio of $\lambda = 4.0$ is averaged over a total of 250 cycles. The acquisition and transformation of the voltage signals from the load cells to dimensional forces are described in detail by LeBlanc [4]. The final signals are filtered using a band-pass filter below 4Hz and above 10Hz. Finally, the loads are binned into $\theta = 5^\circ$ segments with shaded regions representing the standard deviation of each bin.

4 NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL SIMULATIONS COMPARISON

The comparison of CFD simulations and experiments for the primary rotor have been done for the flow fields at several PIV longitudinal locations described above. The comparisons available are of the flow field at positions within XROTOR rotor ($x/R = -0.87, -0.53, -0.13, 0.13, 0.53, 0.87$) for several rotor phase positions ($0^\circ, 45^\circ, 90^\circ$ and 135°) according to the nomenclature described in Figure 6. Also, there are comparisons of the flow field at the wake ($x/R = 0.387, 0.6, 0.75, 0.9, 1.05, 1.35, 1.5, 1.8, 2.1, 2.4$) for the rotor at phase position 0° . For the different locations and rotor positions the fields for U_x , U_z and vorticity X are plotted comparing CFD (left) and experiments (right).

Figure 8 to Figure 19 show the results of the flow field at planes located in ‘campaign 2’ with the rotor at different positions: Figure 8 to Figure 10 (Phase 0°), Figure 11 to Figure 13 (Phase 45°), Figure 14 to Figure 16 (Phase 90°) and Figure 17 to Figure 19 (Phase 135°).

Figure 20 to Figure 22 show the results of the flow field at planes located in ‘campaign 3’ with rotor located at Phase 0° .

CFD simulations allow to obtain the flow field at the complete plane, whereas the PIV measurements has some blind areas when the model blades are present. For instance, at Figure 8, if we look at plane at 0 mm (position of the rotor shaft), the measurements from wind tunnel are only obtained at small area, as the laser is obstructed by the rotor model.

It is observed a good agreement between the wind speed and vorticity distributions obtained by the CFD computations and the wind tunnel experiments. The trends of the flow behaviour at different locations are well matched. Some higher deviations can be observed in the planes located downstream of the rotor. This can be explained as the wind tunnel experiment is

performed in an open jet section, while the CFD computations is performed in a closed contained flow background. Therefore, the boundaries of the wake are different.

4.1 Campaign 2

4.1.1 Phase 0 comparison

Figure 8 Phase 0 UX.

Figure 9 Phase 0 UZ.

Figure 10 Phase 0 Vorticity X.

4.1.2 Phase 45 comparison

Figure 11 Phase 45 UX.

Figure 12 Phase 45 UZ.

Figure 13 Phase 45 Vorticity X.

4.1.3 Phase 90 Comparison

Figure 14 Phase 90 UX.

Figure 15 Phase 90 UZ.

Figure 16 Phase 90 Vorticity X.

4.1.4 Phase 135 comparison

Figure 17 Phase 135 UX.

Figure 18 Phase 135 UZ.

Figure 19 Phase 135 Vorticity X.

4.2 Campaign 3

Figure 20 Phase 0 UX Wake.

Figure 21 Phase 0 UZ Wake.

Figure 22 Phase 0 Vorticity X Wake.

4.3 Forces comparison.

After the analysis of the flow fields, the integrated loads are compared. Figure 23 shows the comparison of the Thrust Coefficient (non-dimensional value of the thrust force) in the X and Y directions and comparing experiments and CFD simulations. The agreement is very good considering that reproducing experimentally and numerically a concept such as XROTOR is very challenging. The agreement for the X direction is higher with similar values of the peak coefficient, mean coefficient and signal period.

Figure 23 CT x and y values. Comparison of simulations (CFD) and experiments.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The main conclusions of the comparison of simulations and experiments for the XROTOR concept are:

1. To simulate and capture properly the flow characteristics in the XROTOR concept the mesh needs to be very refined to model the blade boundary layer and the wake area.
2. Advanced experimental techniques are needed to capture the flow physics of the XROTOR performance and wake.
3. The agreement between experiments and simulations is very good considering that reproducing experimentally and numerically a concept such as XROTOR is very challenging.
4. The agreement in force for the X direction is higher with similar values of the peak coefficient, mean coefficient and signal period. Differences in force at Y direction could be explained for different boundary conditions between experiments and computations (wind tunnel open jet test section vs closed background simulation)

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